

Critical Review on Janapadodhwansa Roga and its Management

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ABSTRACT: Janapadodhwansa is a unique concept explained in Ayurveda which literally means the destruction of a large population. Charak has quoted Janapadodhwansa, (mass destruction) & its 4 reasons as dushitavayu (Air), jala(Water), kala(time), desh(region). Sushrut has already mentioned aupargikarogas (communicable diseases) i.e, kushtha (Skin diseases), jwara (Fever) etc. & their mode of transmission. The root cause for these diseases is said to be Adharma due to prajnaparada. The low socioeconomic status, population explosion, poor hygiene also act as contributory factors. Prevention as well as cure of disease is goal of Ayurveda. Its prime focus on enhancing the immunity of a person . Accordingly, this is achieved by the proper administration of Shodhana and Shamana karma at the proper time. Through maintainance of Dincharaya, Rutucharya, Sadvritta, persons physical and mental health is secured.

KEYWORDS: Janapadodhwans, communicable disease, epidemics, Panchakarma therapy

INTRODUCTION

Janapadodhwansa is derived from Sanskrit word"Janapada" which means the large population and "Udhwansa" which means to destruct. Due to advancement of science and research life span of human being has been increased but simultaneously threat of communicable disease is increasing day by day. Communicable disease spread from one person to another or from an animal to a person. The spread often happens via air borne viruses or bacteria, but also through blood or other bodily fluids. It may also spread easily due to large population, crowd, unhygienic conditions and low immunological status of individual. H1N1 Influenza, Ebola virus are the recent example of such diseases. Because of its contagious nature, a large number of individual are getting infected at the same time thus creating great strain over public health. Ayurveda though being an ancient life science clearly mention's about such disease conditions. A detailed chapter on Janapadodhwans in Charak Samhita Vimansthan 3rd Adhyay explains epidemic disease and its etiological factors. In Sushrut samhita Kushthanidanadhyay there is a good description on mode of transfer of disease. They are called Aupasargikrogas (Communicable diseases). From these references we come to know that in ancient time also there were such epidemics.

The first line of management of these Janapadodhwamsakara Vyadhi's starts with panchkarma^[1]. Panchakarma plays a huge role in exhibiting 3-fold benefits of Mahaphalam which means Prevention by removing alimentary toxins, Rogaharam by Curing the diseases, Bala varna prasadanam by promoting Rejuvenation action. Thus, this paper mainly highlights the understanding of different views of Communicable diseases and the importance of various chikitsa principles of Janapadodhwamsakara vyadhi's.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Janapadodhwans Defination

Charak Samhita Vimansthan 3rd Adhyaya Acharya Charak has described the term Janapadodhwans meaning destruction of a population living in an area.

It is similar with epidemics.

People having different prakruti, sarata and aahar but some factors like air, region are common to them and vitiation of these factors leads to disease production and death which is termed as Janapadodhwans^[2]

ORIGIN OF JANAPADODHWAMSA

Acharya Charaka has mentioned the foremost reason for Janapadodhwamsa is Adharma (immorality). The root cause of Adharm is said to be Pragyaparadha (delinquency of wisdom).

Asatmyayendriyarthasamyoga, Pragyaparadha and parinama has been described as the main factors for development of any disease^[3] The word Pragyaparadha is made from two words pragya+ aparadh. Pragya= Dhee+ Dhriti+ Smruti, and apradh means misdemeanour. Deranged Dhee(intellect), dhriti (Patience), and Smriti (memory) leads to all sorts of Ashubh karma (unwholesome/ inauspicious actions). This is called as pragyaparadha and causes vitiation of all Doshas^[4,5] Pragyaparadha is even said to be the cause of all Aagantuka (exogenous) and Manasika (mental) Vyadhi^[6]

Acharya Charaka has also described Lobha (greed) as a factor leading to Adharma. Further, reason for Bhutasangha (contact with an organism) Abhishapa (curse) has also been described as Adharma^[7] Lobha (greed) along with Abhidroha (affronting) and kopa (anger) has also been mentioned as etiological factors for the occurrence of eight major diseases^[8] Acharya Sushruta has mentioned that the reason behind the change in Maraka is Adrishta (invisible or idiopathic). Further Dalhana explains these to be caused by the Adharma (immorality) of population of that particular area. Sometimes the Ritu Vyapad (seasonal variations) may also be caused due to various reasons like Abhishaap (curse), Rakshkrodh (demon resentment)etc^[9]

Factors causing Janpadodhwans

- ✓ Janapadodhwans occurs due to vitiation of vayu, jala, desh, kala.
They are nothing but modes by which infectious diseases spread^[10]
- ✓ Acharya Charaka has mentioned Adharma as the root cause of Janapadodhwans.
Not following one's duty to a community is termed as adharm. Pradnyaparadh is also included in it.
- ✓ Not following Dincharya(daily regimen), ritucharya(seasonal regimen), Vegavidharan (suppression of urges), paapkarma (sins) is included in Adharma.
All these things are responsible for hampering immunity of an individual.
Thus not directly but surely Adharma is responsible for Janapadodhwans.
- ✓ Sushrut Samhita Nidansthan Adhyaya 4th Kushthnidanadhyaya
Acharya Sushrut has mentioned Aupasargikrogas in Kushthanidan.
They are contagious diseases which spread through direct contact or contaminated objects of patient.
- ✓ By physical contact, expired air, eating with others in same plate, sharing bed (sexual contact also) using clothes, garlands and paste (anulepa or cosmetics) infectious diseases spread from person to person^[11]

Characteristics of polluted air, water, land and time:

Air with following characteristics is injurious to health:

Atistimitam aticalam – Excessive calmness or violent blows

Atiparuṣam atīṣitam atyuṣṇam atirūḡṣam atyabhiṣyandinam – Excessive dryness, cold, hot air, roughness or humidity

Atibhairavārāvatipratihata – excessive clashes among each other (wind blowing from one direction clashing with the one from the other)

Paraspara gatim atikuṇḡalinam – excessively cyclonic in nature and

Asātmyagandha bāṣpasikatāpāṡsudhūmopahatamiti – association with unwholesome smell, gases, sand, ashes and smoke

Water that can cause endemic diseases:

Vikrutgandhavarnarasasparṣa- (Abnormal smell colour, taste, and touch)

Jalcharavihangam- (water bodies is devoid of aquatic animals like fishes etc.)

Kledabahula- (excessive stickiness)

Upgatagunam -(devoid of natural qualities)

Upkshinamjaleshaya -(reduced water levels in lakes and ponds)

Aritikaram- (unpleasant appearance or taste)

Land having the following characteristics is considered to be harmful:

Prakṛti vikṛta varṇa gandha rasa sparṣam – Abnormal color, smell, taste and touch

Kleda bahulam – Excessive stickiness, Abundance of serpents, wild animals, mosquitoes, locusts, flies, rats, owls, vulture and jackal

Pratānādi bahulam – Having excess of grass and weeds

Apūrvavadapatita – Abundance of excessively branched creepers having a novel look

śuṣkanaṣṡasasyam – withered, dried

Dhūmravānam – Abundance of smoke in the wind, Presence of wild cries of birds and dogs

Kala

Features opposite to the normal course of season, excessive or less to the features of normal course of season

Line of treatment of epidemic diseases:

Ayurvedic Management of communicable disease

Some diseases are incurable if arishta lakshana (fatal signs) are present, while others even without such signs are incurable because of certain purvajanmakrut karma (fatal past deeds).

Ayurveda emphasizes on treatment of sadhyavyadhis only. Thus treatment of those who don't show the fatal signs is mentioned in the following quotation^[12]

1. Karma Panchavidham (Appropriate use of Panchakarma)

Vaman, Virechan, Niruhabasti, anuvasan basti and shirovirechan are panchakarma described by AcharyaCharak. AcharyaSushrut and Acharya vagbhat included raktamokshana

Role Of Panchakarma In Communicable Diseases

Vamana karma: vamana has a significant role in preventing diseases and also in preventing the complications that may arise due to various communicable diseases. when vamana is administered in a systematic way the patient will be benefited from the vamana phala such as preventing kasa, Upalepa, Swarabheda, Nidra, Tandra, Asyadourgandha, Vishopasarga, Kapha praseka, Grahani dosha^[13] Samyak Vamana does “Hrit parshwa murdha indriya margashuddhi” which indicates that there are fewer chances for

the external factors to invade the body, Thus, Vamana acts as both a primary preventive and Tertiary preventive method.

Virechana Karma: Supreme procedure for eliminating vitiated pitta dosha and pitta associated with kapha and pitta sthanagata kapha. virechana enhances bala, varna facilitates sroto shuddhi, prevents communicable diseases arising due to vitiated pitta dosha. By removal of water, how all dependents of water get destroyed, in the same way, by the removal of vitiated pitta, all diseases due to pitta dosha get subsided^[14]

Basti Karma: Basti is one of the panchakarma procedures that is supreme for acting on dooshita vata . vayu is sarvatra and is responsible for maintaining various systems of the body. Acharya charaka has compared the action of basti karma with the watering of plants at their roots. Basti when administered through the anus in the rectum and colon, reaches the entire body and eliminates the impairment of vata dosha which causes various symptoms in different infectious diseases, Different Yapanabasti, Madhutailika basti, Matra basti, Yuktaratha basti, Bala varnakara basti can be administered after proper diagnosis, and later the permutations and combinations of drugs can be administered in the form of basti in the patient to avoid the further impact of the infections on the body. Basti also aims at Srotoshodhanarta and balavarnakartva which is a primary goal is enhancing the vyadhishamatva of the person.

2. Rasayana therapy:

According to Acharya charaka rasayana therapy is of 2 type

a. Promotive: It is two type

1. Which provides strength and immunity to healthy person. The rasayana is of 2 types
ie. Kutipraveshik and vatatapika.

2. Which promotes sexual vigor vajikaran

b. Curative- Treatment which cures the diseases

IMPORTANCE OF RASAYANA

Several Rasayana botanicals described in Ayurveda are used in clinical practice for strengthening immunity. Based on our research data, we find Ashwagandha (*Withaniasomnifera*), Guduchi (*Tinoporacordifolia*), Shatavari (*Asparagus racemosus*), Amalaki (*phylanthusembelica*), and Yashtimadhu (*Glycerizaglabra*) are potential immunomodulators.

According to kalpadruma Rasayana means rasaraktadi dhatus (the seven basic tissues) reaches their proper destination or the process which help in proper nourishment of tissues by poshaka rasa. According to Sushruta, Rasayanatantra includes different steps of delaying aging process, increases longevity, and intelligence and provide disease resistant power to the individual.^[15]

According to Charaka Rasayana is the method to produce the dhatus of optimum quality. According to Sharangdhara, Rasayana treatment is one which result in the prevention of diseases due to old age.^[16]

DHUPANAA KARMA (FUMIGATION)

In ancient time and even today Yagya are done for the welfare of the mass population as it resulted in mass hygiene. It is also mentioned in Janapadodhvamsa in Ayurvedic literatures. In Kashyap Samhita, Raksoghana Dhupana is mentioned for protection from infections and Gana Dhupana for all diseases originating from Bhuta (microbes)^[17]. In Charaka and Sushruta Samhita different type of Dravyas i.e drugs are mentioned in

different diseases that are used for Dhupana Karma. Like, Guggulu (Commiphora mukul), Nimba (Azadiractaindica), Vacha (Acorus Calamus), Kutha (Saussurealappa), Haritaki (Terminalia Chebula), Sarsapa (Brassica campestris), Yava (Hordeumvulgare) with ghrita^[18]. In Sushruta Samhita, Rakshoghna Dravya are mentioned like Sarsapa, Nimba, Lavana with ghrita fumigation with them to be done twice a day for 10 days. Microbes are destroyed by Rakshoghana drugs^[19]

VAAD CHIKITSA (SOUND THERAPY)

Acharya Sushruta said that if food is contaminated with poison, then different symptoms arises due to that poison and to treat them apply different pastes on various types of instruments and produce sound from them. Equal parts of each of these contents, Taar (Silver). Sutaar (Mercury), Suvarna (Gold), Saariva and Kuruvind (A kind of precious stone or Mustai.ecyperus) total of above four dravya, these should be mixed with pitta of cow of Kapila Varna (color). This paste should be applied on sound producing instruments. As from the sound of instruments Ghor visha will be destroyed^[20]

3. Achar Rasayana and Sadvrittapan

Truthfulness

Bhoote Daya – compassion for living beings

Dana – donation, charity

Bali – scarifies

Devatarchana – prayer to the gods

Sadvrutta – good deeds adoption of preventive measures, tranquility, protection of the self by Mantra etc are very effective. ^[21]

Traditional methods of water purification in india

For centuries, natures various products and womens knowledge of their properties have provided the basis for making water safe for drinking.

The sushrut samhita describes modes of purifying water, among which is the clarification of muddy water by natural coagulants such as the nuts of the nirmali tree (strychnos potatorium).

The seeds of nirmali tree are used to clear muddy water by rubbing them on inside of vessels in which it is stored.

Seeds of honge (pongamia glabra) are similarly used

Dhavashwakarnadi yog in purification of polluted water

This yog is given in sushrut samhita kalpasthan adhyay 3 in samarik visha prakaran. It contains

1)Ashwakarn

2)Asaan

3)Paribhadra

4)Patala

5)Siddhak

6)Mokshak

7)Amaltas

8)Somvalka

This all herbs should be burn into ash and then this ash should be poured in vessel containing one anjali water. This how the water is purified^[22]

Herbs used in purification of air

Here are now another herbs used for purification of polluted air given in sushrut samhita.

- 1)Haridra
- 2)Tamalpatra
- 3)Kuth
- 4)Priyangu
- 5)Lakha

This herbs are put on sacred fire called yadnya and by this polluted air is purified.

CONCLUSION

Modern lifestyle is a major factor in exploitation of nature. Increase in the rate of industrialization have left air, land and water polluted. Due to these polluted air, land and water leads to the spread of infectious diseases. In ancient time also acharyas had the knowledge about communicable diseases. Treatment such as panchakarma and use of Rasayana as mainstream treatment. As the main objective of Ayurveda is Swasthasya Swasthya Rakshanam i.e maintain health of healthy person. Prevention is the best way to avoid Aupsargik vyadhi (communicable diseases) Good immunity plays an important role in prevention and cure of epidemic diseases. Rasayan therapy, panchakarma, sadvritta palan and Acharrasayana, yagya should be tried as preventive measure.

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